

Design and material options to fight against surface contamination and approaches to reduce the amount of patient-fall injuries

Prepared for: for all interested persons

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

OBJECTIVE

The object of this study is the possibility of using modern means of constant exposure to reduce the pathogenic flora on the surface of objects in combination with the properties of objects to prevent and reduce injuries from falls.

GOALS

To substantiate the need for antimicrobial additives in the composition of wall protection systems materials often used in all public institutions.

Demonstrate the need for continued handrails to prevent and reduce injury from falls.

To show how these two goals can be combined in one product and type of material, which will synergistically produce significantly positive results for the public.

SOLUTION

A new way to use ionpure silver as an antimicrobial agent in ARFEN wall protection systems effectively affects the pathogenic flora. Therefore, significantly reducing its amount helps prevent the spread of diseases.

This material in ARFEN handrails and other wall protection materials, combined with antimicrobial action and fall injury prevention, will save many lives.

SUMMARY

It has been proven and given enough evidence that silver ion, which is used to manufacture ARFEN products, significantly reduces the spread of pathogenic flora, including SARS-Cov viruses.

There is evidence and ample evidence that the use of handrails, in combination with new design codes, significantly reduces the incidence of grass from falls.

The validity of ARFEN products in combination with antimicrobial effects is shown in the struggle to improve the population's quality of life.

PART 1: DESIGN AND MATERIAL OPTIONS TO FIGHT AGAINST SURFACE CONTAMINATION

1. INTRODUCTION

As we assess what the COVID-19 pandemic situation showed us, keeping interior spaces clean can help avoid such problems in the future.

It is evident that there is no guarantee that a building can stay away from sickness and infection spread; we expect cleaning measures to become more strict to ensure the safety and comfort of guests, staff, patients, and residents.

2. MITIGATING THE SPREAD

For the past 15 years, the healthcare industry has focused on preventing cross-contamination. The mission of environmental management and services was the destruction of nosocomial infections. First, it was essential to understand the transmission routes and then counteract with cleaning and disinfection.

As a result, choosing suitable building materials has become equally important. As a result, healthcare facilities have reported reductions in HAI across the country through education, training, tracking, and measuring outcomes.

Our environment is such that the number of diseases transmitted in society is increasing as bacteria and viruses are found in institutions. So it is to our advantage to take the lessons learned from healthcare and apply them across the built environment.

Both viruses and bacteria come in different forms, but both are looking for a host. That is us! Many are transferred with direct human-to-human contact, but scientific research has shown us that microbes can survive for periods on surfaces and act as an intermediary for transmission.

For this white paper, we will focus on materials that keep bacterial life, viruses, and molds at bay, making them unable to colonize and using disinfectants to infect them.

This study is aimed to estimate the antimicrobial potential of our ARFEN wall protection materials, which can be covered with antimicrobial PVC or TPE, which contain the best ion pure silver in the market produced by Ishizuka, Japan¹.

Most studies show that using unique silver or zinc additives can eliminate 99.9% of the *E. coli* and 99.7 % of the *S. aureus* population and present an inhibition zone in the fungal assay, reducing the spread of SARS-Cov viruses.²

3. WHAT ARE THE LEGALITIES?

Nevertheless, before jumping in, there are legalities to understand:

1. Impure is FIFRA (The Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act) approved. EPA-approved Ion pure can be used for non-food contact, food contact, and drinking water applications. For example, polymer incorporated applications, PVC wall protection systems, Tupperware, artificial countertops, drinking water filters, and ice machine applications. (ION PURE ZAF (73148-2), ION PURE IZA (73148-5), ION PURE ZAF HS (73148-6), ION PURE ZAF MS (73148-7), ION PURE IPI (73148-8))³.
2. Impure is FDA (Food and Drug Administration) approved. Ion pure can be used for industrial polymers, industrial packaging, or packaging applications. Listed applications are food wrapping applications, trays, bottles, containers used for the delivery of food (FCN No. 000432 ION PURE IPL, FCN No. 000433 ION PURE WPA, FCN No. 000476 ION PURE IZA)⁴.
3. Impure is listed under NSF (National Sanitation Foundation) approved substance under NSF Standard 51. With this registration, ion pure can be applied in polymeric applications⁵,

¹ <https://www.ishizuka.co.jp/english/material/antimicrobial/#date01>

² Antimicrobial Performance of Thermoplastic Elastomers Containing Zinc Pyrithione and Silver Nanoparticles by Michele Pistol, Daiane Tomacheski, Douglas Naue Simões, Vanda Ferreira Ribeiro, Ruth Marlene Campomanes Santana

³ Inorganic silver antimicrobial "IONPURE" | ISHIZUKA GLASS CO <https://www.ishizuka.co.jp/english/material/antimicrobial/>

⁴ Inorganic silver antimicrobial "IONPURE" | ISHIZUKA GLASS CO <https://www.ishizuka.co.jp/english/material/antimicrobial/>

⁵ Inorganic silver antimicrobial "IONPURE" | ISHIZUKA GLASS CO <https://www.ishizuka.co.jp/english/material/antimicrobial/>

even in food contact settings. NSF Standard 51 (ION PURE WPA, ION PURE IPL, ION PURE IZA)⁶.

This is at the core of how we will move forward with developing limited cross-contamination when using this active agent in ARFEN's wall protection systems materials.

4. SURFACES AS PATHS OF TRANSMISSION

Infectious agents are associated with providing medical care, mainly from humans, but contaminated objects and environmental substances - e.g., air, food, water, tabletops, and other surfaces can be transmitted from one person to another. As a result, patients, medical staff, family members, and other visitors are carriers of responsible microbes.⁷

Germes move by touch. For example, when healthcare workers touch medical equipment, their hands become contaminated by touching germs present on that equipment or surfaces. They carry germs on their hands and can spread them to susceptible people if proper hand hygiene is performed prior to touching. Attention should be paid to thorough hand washing. Many public health experts extol the benefits of hand-washing in slowing the spread of disease - and they are right! This can help reduce the overall amount of germs on your hands.

However, the benefit of hand-washing or using "sanitizing" hand gels in reducing transmission is predicated on two key factors: Did the person wash/gel their hands, and 2) did their hands get truly sterile by doing so?

The unfortunate answer to both questions is no. Research leads to several cases where people do not wash their hands after using the toilet or between patients in case of medical care. Furthermore, another drawback is that people do not often wash long enough to drastically reduce the number of germs, viruses, and spores on their skin.

Therefore, materials with antimicrobial properties of permanent exposure are necessary for the overall struggle for the population's health.

⁶ Inorganic silver antimicrobial "IONPURE" | ISHIZUKA GLASS CO <https://www.ishizuka.co.jp/english/material/antimicrobial/>

⁷ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings: Do They Help Reduce Healthcare-Associated Infections? Ted Schettler MD, MPH March 2016

MICROBES OF ALL KINDS CAN BE RESTORED ON SURFACES

Current evidence suggests that SARS-CoV-2 can persist for hours to days on foci made from volumes of various materials.

In addition, medical researchers observed sensitivity to microbes in the middle tissues., including those used in privacy curtains. For example, a study at Shriners Hospital for Children showed that staphylococcus bacteria survived up to 56 days on polyester-type fabrics, and the shortest - 11 days. The point is that 11 days is more than enough time to acquire and transfer based on touch.⁸

The fact is that the type of surface - porous or nonporous - and in ANY salon - can play a role in how long a bacterium can outlive.

AEROSOLE WHEN SNEEZING AND COUGHING

When an infected person coughs or sneezes, splashes occur and form droplets that carry microbes (approximately 6 ft). These germs can get into a susceptible person's eyes, nose, or mouth and cause an infection (whooping cough or meningitis).

The CDC states that the coronavirus is more common through respiratory droplets and aerosols than through touching objects and surfaces.

However, evidence suggests the SARS-CoV-2 virus may remain for hours to days on various materials. ⁹ Moreover, the CDC recommends cleaning and disinfection of surfaces as a best practice to prevent the spread of COVID-19 and other viral illnesses.

However, is it possible to ensure that all surfaces are always disinfected? Not.

⁸ Survival of Enterococci and Staphylococci on Hospital Fabrics and Plastic Authors: Alice N. Neely, Matthew P. Maley [ASM Journals/ Journal of Clinical Microbiology / Vol. 38, No. 2](#)

⁹ Contamination of inert surfaces by SARS-CoV-2: Persistence, stability, and infectivity. A review Author: MontseMarquès, José L. Domingo.

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DON'T LOSE SIGHT OF MOLD.

Talking about pandemics, it is easy to overlook a mold and its effects. Unfortunately, it is easy to overlook a mold and its impacts with all the talk of pandemics.

Exposure to moldy environments may cause health effects or none at all. Some people are sensitive to mold. People may develop mold with symptoms such as nasal congestion, wheezing, redness, or itching in the eyes or skin. Some people with mold allergies or asthma may have more intense reactions.

NO BUILDING IS IMMUNE.

If only we imagine we touch hundreds of surfaces every day, from bathroom fixtures to door handles and then the tables where we eat, from the edges of curtains to shopping cart handles. However, if we have found anything, bacteria and fungi may be found on these surfaces.

Much of the response to the COVID pandemic has focused on Healthcare workers and hospitals. However, we emphasize that every building or facility is immune. Moreover, due to many people entering there and working, public buildings of all types have an increased transmission potential and require increased vigilance.

Therefore, permanent passive, active protection in the form of handrails with antibacterial properties and wall coverings with materials of the same properties in very crowded places can serve as one of the ways to reduce the spread of diseases actively.

5. ENVIRONMENTAL SURFACES

Contaminated environmental surfaces are important potential links in the transmission pathway of pathogens from one person to another¹⁰. Microbes can colonize virtually any surface and persist for weeks on materials commonly used in hospitals, including stainless steel and various plastic polymers. For example, MRSA (methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*)

¹⁰ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

can persist on surfaces for more than six months.¹¹¹² Spore-forming *C. difficile* can also persist for up to a year or more.¹³ These surfaces can be a source of microbes with the potential to be transmitted without regular cleaning and disinfection.¹⁴¹⁵

Current guidelines recommend that surfaces in patient rooms be cleaned and disinfected routinely (e.g., daily or three times weekly) and when a patient is moved or discharged from the room (terminal cleaning)¹⁶. High-touch surfaces, such as doorknobs, bed rails, over-bed tables, call buttons, IV poles, and surfaces in and around toilets, probably play a role more frequently in microbial transmission than lower-touch surfaces, even though studies show that the microbial load on high- touch surfaces is only slightly higher before cleaning and disinfection than lower-touch surfaces.

Given the persistent problem of HAIs despite existing infection control programs, interest in the development and deployment of antimicrobial technologies built into materials on high-touch and other surfaces in hospitals is growing¹⁷. It is based on two observations: 1) environmental surfaces can harbor pathogens for long periods, and 2) cleaning and disinfection of surfaces are often inadequate. It is also based on a presumption that has rarely been verified: regularly reducing surface microbial load below a certain level by methods and standardized cleaning and disinfection practices will reduce the risk of transmission of pathogens by health care workers or others, thereby reducing the incidence of HAIs¹⁸.

¹¹ Wagenvoort J, Sluijsmans W, Penders R. Better environmental survival of outbreak vs. sporadic MRSA isolates. J. Hosp. Infect. 2000; 45:231–234.

¹² Kramer A, Schwebke I, Kampf G. How long do nosocomial pathogens persist on inanimate surfaces? BMC Infect Dis. 2006; Aug 16:6:130.

¹³ Schmidt M, Attaway H, Sharpe P, John J, et al. Sustained reduction of microbial burden on joint hospital surfaces through the introduction of copper. J Clin Microbiol. 2012; 50(7):2217-2223.

¹⁴ Martínez J, Ruthazer R, Hansjosten K, Barefoot L, Snyderman D. Role of environmental contamination as a risk factor for acquiring vancomycin-resistant *enterococci* in patients treated in a medical intensive care unit. Arch. Intern. Med. 2003; 163:1905–1912.

¹⁵ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

¹⁶ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

¹⁷ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

¹⁸ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

SCHOOLS

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 22 million sick days are taken each year due to the common cold alone¹⁹. So, with even more severe concerns over influenza, the microbiologists at NSF International wanted to experiment to find out where germs were most commonly found in local schools²⁰.

Two Michigan elementary schools were selected to take part in this experiment. A range of bacterial samples was taken from²¹ various surfaces that kids come in contact with every day at school. This experiment aimed to determine what teachers and school cleaners should pay attention to protect children from germs. The tables below contain information that the number of microbes on the surface has been exceeded:

Figure 1. Total Aerobic Bacteria per Square Inch

Sample Location	(Colony Forming Units / in sq)
Water Fountain Spigot (classroom)	2,700,000 CFU/in sq
Water Fountain Spigot (cafeteria)	62,000 CFU/in sq
Plastic Reusable Cafeteria Tray	33,800 CFU/in sq
Faucet (cold water handle)	32,000 CFU/in sq
Faucet (hot water handle)	18,000 CFU/in sq
Cafeteria Plate	15,800 CFU/in sq
Keyboard (classroom)	3,300 CFU/in sq
Toilet Seat	3,200 CFU/in sq
Student's Hand	1,200 CFU/in sq
Animal Cage	1,200 CFU/in sq

Source: NSF.org

Surprisingly, the study revealed more germs found on an average classroom water fountain spigot than on a toilet seat. Although these findings are a snapshot in time at these particular

¹⁹ Germiest Places at Schools | NSF International. <https://www.nsf.org/blog/consumer/germiest-places-schools>

²⁰ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

²¹ Germiest Places at Schools | NSF International. <https://www.nsf.org/blog/consumer/germiest-places-schools>

schools, the results reveal that we need to be vigilant about sanitizing hard-to-reach areas in schools²² and those surfaces that people may forget to regularly clean and sanitize.²³

The good news is that school surfaces might be protected by using unique antibacterial coverings that ARFEN manufactures. In addition, Wall protection and handrails are manufactured using protective ingredients known as ionpure silver.

HOTELS

A new preliminary study indicates the existence of such a concept that: about 81% of hotel room surfaces contain samples of some fecal contamination.²⁴ Moreover, television remotes are, in fact, among the most bacteria-laden surfaces, ranking up there with toilets and bathroom sinks. The findings were presented on June 17 at the American Society for Microbiology's 2012 general meeting.

For the research, the team sampled for bacterial contamination²⁵²⁶ on 18 different surfaces in nine hotel rooms across three states (Indiana, South Carolina, and Texas). The light switch, carpet, and telephone also had high levels of these bugs, which included the full workup of aerobic and coliform bacteria, not all of which will make us sick²⁷, but some of which can—and many of which could pose a threat to those with compromised immune systems.

The team also found, perhaps not surprisingly, that many cleaning items in housekeeping carts, such as mops and sponges²⁸, have high bacteria levels. The concern here is that these implements could easily transmit harmful bacteria from one surface or room to another.

²² Germiest Places at Schools | NSF International. <https://www.nsf.org/blog/consumer/germiest-places-schools>

²³ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

²⁴ <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/2012/05/30/mens-offices-harbor-more-bacteria-than-womens/>

²⁵ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article.cfm?id=human-fecal-bacterium-cau>

²⁶ Hotel Rooms' Most Bacteria-Laden Surfaces? Don't Touch <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/hotel-rooms-most-bacteria-laden-surfaces-dont-touch-that-dial/>

²⁷ Hotel Rooms' Most Bacteria-Laden Surfaces? Don't Touch <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/hotel-rooms-most-bacteria-laden-surfaces-dont-touch-that-dial/>

²⁸ Hotel Rooms' Most Bacteria-Laden Surfaces? Don't Touch <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/hotel-rooms-most-bacteria-laden-surfaces-dont-touch-that-dial/>

The findings are not just meant to paralyze the anxious traveler with germ-induced fear. "Hoteliers must provide their guests²⁹ with a safe and secure environment," Katie Kirsch, one of the researchers and an undergraduate at the University of Houston, said in a prepared statement³⁰³¹. "Currently, housekeeping practices vary across brands and properties with little or no standardization industry-wide." So how do housekeepers and managers tell if a hotel room is clean enough? The same way we inspect our rooms: "visual assessment," Kirsch said, "which is ineffective in measuring levels of sanitation," presumably even the white-glove-across-the-baseboard method³².

A little science could at least guide housekeeping policy, she noted. The study was designed to apply food safety's Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points³³ System to hotel environments for the first time. Hotel employees spend an average of about half an hour cleaning and preparing each room, so, she said, "identifying high-risk items within a hotel room would allow housekeeping managers to strategically design cleaning practices and allocate time to efficiently reduce the potential health risks posed by microbial contamination in hotel rooms." In other words, managers could suggest spending less time dusting off that bedside Bible and more time wiping down the TV remote.³⁴³⁵

The good news is that hotel surfaces might be protected by using unique antibacterial coverings that ARFEN manufacturers. In addition, Wall protection and handrails are manufactured using protective ingredients known as ionpure silver.

²⁹ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/podcast/episode.cfm?id=FC1B957F-ECE5-FA78-69885F893440286B>

³⁰ www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2012-06/asfm-tmc061312.php

³¹ Hotel Rooms' Most Bacteria-Laden Surfaces? Don't Touch <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/hotel-rooms-most-bacteria-laden-surfaces-dont-touch-that-dial/>

³² Hotel Rooms' Most Bacteria-Laden Surfaces? Don't Touch <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/hotel-rooms-most-bacteria-laden-surfaces-dont-touch-that-dial/>

³³ www.who.int/foodsafety/fs_management/haccp/en/

³⁴ Hotel Rooms' Most Bacteria-Laden Surfaces? Don't Touch <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/hotel-rooms-most-bacteria-laden-surfaces-dont-touch-that-dial/>

³⁵ Hotel Rooms' Most Bacteria-Laden Surfaces? Do Not Touch That Dial Author: [Katherine Harmon](#) on June 20, 2012

SENIOR ACCOMMODATION

The Center for Medicaid Services (CMS) recognized infection as the "leading cause of morbidity and mortality" in 15,600 nursing homes. Under the proposed rules, the agency announced that between 1.6 million and 3.8 million cases occur in facilities each year, with almost 388,000 deaths from infections.

CBS News has convened a study group to uncover cleanliness in commercial centers.

The group included Charles Gerba and Dr. Philip Tierno. Now we might be thinking, "What do malls have to do with qualified nursing homes?" hang there. Here is what the doctors said:

"During our research, we found that food was a stick, urine, mucus, feces, and blood on the escalator handrails," Gerba says. "And where there is mucus, you can also find cold and pleasure viruses." Tierno Respiratory Correspondence: "We are seeing flora on the railings," he says, "which makes sense because people are coughing in their hands and then touching³⁶ the railings."

There is no need for Ph.D. in epidemiology to see the connection here. For example, skilled employment establishments have handrails almost everywhere to help **adjust to** mobility and stability. Furthermore, with rising acuity, even assisted living facilities may need to install handrails, even though it may conflict with the residential-style living space these facilities try to achieve and maintain.

Point: Handrails can be a focal point of disease spread, so using specially manufactured handrails as ARFEN is important.

Coronavirus draws attention to the problems. At the time of this writing, more than 16,000 residents and caregivers have died from COVID-19.

Moreover, nearly 97,000 residents and staff have tested positive for the virus. However, those figures are an undercount because testing has been limited, and many states have not released complete data.

³⁶ Creeping Illness – Site Title - WordPress.com. <https://schneidersview.wordpress.com/2017/12/06/creeping-illness/>

The good news is that senior living surfaces might be protected using unique antibacterial coverings that ARFEN manufacturers use. In addition, Wall protection and handrails are manufactured using protective ingredients known as ionpure silver.

COMMERCIAL BATHROOMS

When we stay in a hotel room, we usually expect that the staff has cleaned it thoroughly after the last guest stayed there. However, this is not always the case, and even regular cleaning can leave travelers open to other people's germs, experts say.

In one 2012 study³⁷ presented at the general meeting of the American Society of Microbiology, 81% of surfaces sampled³⁸³⁹ had some fecal bacteria. Researchers found that light switches and TV remotes were among the objects most heavily contaminated with bacteria, and toilets and bathroom sinks also had high levels of microbial organisms.

This is not surprising, says Kelly Reynolds, germ expert and associate professor of environmental health at⁴⁰ the University of Arizona, because hard surfaces frequently touched by multiple people provide suitable environments for microbes to collect. For example, whenever we touch a light switch or TV remote, microbes from our hands transfer to the new object. In addition, Reynolds says that items like the hotel phone or a keyboard also harbor lots of germs.

When it comes to the bathroom, most surfaces around the toilet are likely pretty dirty. "When you flush the toilet, the viruses and the feces do get spread throughout the walls of the toilet, the flush handle, and the walls of the bathroom," says Reynolds.

In a recent study in the American Journal of Infection Control, Reynolds and her colleagues found that flushing a toilet can send contaminants flying not only on the toilet seat but also onto the floor and the back of the toilet (more than 80% of the time), the wall behind the toilet (nearly

³⁷ The Germiest Spots in Your Hotel Room By Alexandra Sifferlin June 18, 2012

³⁸ Hotel Rooms' Most Bacteria-Laden Surfaces? Do Not Touch That Dial By Katherine Harmon on June 20, 2012, <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/hotel-rooms-most-bacteria-laden-surfaces-dont-touch-that-dial/>

³⁹ Dirty Hotel Room: These Are the Germiest Places - Time. <https://time.com/5135121/dirty-hotel-rooms-germs/>

⁴⁰ Dirty Hotel Room: These Are the Germiest Places - Time. <https://time.com/5135121/dirty-hotel-rooms-germs/>

40% of the time), the flush handle (22% of the time) and the toilet paper dispenser (17% of the time)⁴¹.

The good news is that commercial bathrooms might be protected by using unique antibacterial coverings that ARFEN manufacturers. In addition, Wall protection and handrails are manufactured using protective ingredients known as ion pure silver.

OLD DORMITORIES ARE PARTICULARLY SUSCEPTIBLE TO MOLD

In only one case of the existing students at the University of Tennessee at Knoxville, did the dormitory have to be evacuated?

They are moving a week before the interim dates increased stress to stress. One medical student, Megan Wilson, told The Chronicle of Higher Education. "I understand housing is possible," she said. "But it is uncomfortable to deal with, making my semester more difficult than before."

The problem of mold in dormitories is widely-spread. For example, the New York Times found the health hazards of moldy dorms in August 2019 and cited cases spreading from Oklahoma to Washington DC to Rhode Island. In addition, there are reports in the media - almost impossible to list - of students complaining of chronic coughs, headaches, blocked sinuses, asthma, earaches, shortness of breath, and the list goes on.

Factors leading to mold:

- Old tile and grout,
- Broken tile,
- Humid climates,
- Poor and infrequent cleaning.

The good news is that ARFEN's wall protection systems materials surface with antibacterial inserts completely mold resistance.

⁴¹ Dirty Hotel Room: These Are the Germiest Places - Time. <https://time.com/5135121/dirty-hotel-rooms-germs/>

MOLD LITIGATION CASES GROWTH

Mold litigation against universities and colleges is coming out of the starting gate. In one case, more than 20 students of the University of India sued a school after experiencing mold in their dorms. According to an article in the Indiana Daily Student on April 28, 2019:

When students got mold on Foster and McNutt's ATVs last semester, those who lived in the dorms received compensation totaling more than \$7.3 million.

IU's evidence is also based on the Indiana Reduction Act, limiting the amount a government agency can pay to solve a crime to \$5 million. Lawyers for IU upload that \$7.3 million is already more than the university can be attracted to flow under the law.⁴²

Therefore, the use of mold-resistant materials such as ARFEN's wall protection systems combined with antibacterial properties can significantly improve the quality of life for many people⁴³.

6. ANTIMICROBIALS IN PRODUCTS: MATERIAL PRESERVATION VS. PATHOGEN REDUCTION

Antimicrobials can be added to materials and products for two general reasons. First, many materials and products, including wood, polymers, adhesives, foams, and fabrics, are susceptible to damage from microorganisms that can thrive on embedded nutrients. Because of this, biocides are frequently added to protect the material from degradation and prevent stains and odor from microbial contamination during product use. Second, antimicrobials may be added to a product - or a product manufactured from materials with antimicrobial properties - to reduce microbial colonization with human pathogens. If this rationale is claimed or implied by a manufacturer, the EPA considers it a health-related claim, and it carries with it a burden to examine the safety and efficacy of the agent or material in greater detail than if it is used solely for material preservation⁴⁴.

⁴² IU wins 2018 mold infestation lawsuit in appeals court By Lauren McLaughlin Published March 21, 2021

⁴³ Research drives changes to make hearing health ... - NIDCD. <https://www.nidcd.nih.gov/about/nidcd-director-message/research-drives-changes-make-hearing-health-care-more-accessible-and-affordable>

⁴⁴ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

Under the Biocidal Product Regulation (BPR), a biocide is defined as a chemical substance or microorganism intended to destroy, deter, render harmless, or exert a controlling effect on any harmful organism by chemical or biological means. The BPR requires registration of active ingredients, and once registered, biocides must undergo a testing and review process, regardless of the purpose of their use⁴⁵.

In the United States, the EPA defines biocides as “a diverse group of poisonous substances including preservatives, insecticides, disinfectants, and pesticides used to control organisms that are harmful to human or animal health or that cause damage to natural or manufactured products .” Although the EPA definition includes plant protection products and some veterinary medicines, the two definitions are similar. Thus, a biocide can be a pesticide, including fungicides, herbicides, insecticides, algicides, molluscicides, miticides, rodenticides, and antimicrobials, including germicides, and antibiotics, antibacterials, antivirals, antifungals, antiprotozoals, and anti parasites⁴⁶.

Additionally, within the United States, the Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act (FIFRA) authorize and requires federal regulation of the distribution, sale, and use of pesticides to protect human health and the environment. Products that kill or repel bacteria or germs are considered pesticides and must be registered with the EPA prior to distribution or sale. The EPA will not register a pesticide until tested to show that it will not pose an unreasonable risk when used according to the directions. This includes pesticides used on textiles to provide antimicrobial or other pesticidal characteristics. In addition, FIFRA does not allow companies to make public health pesticide claims for any product distributed or sold unless the product has been approved and registered by the EPA or is covered by an exemption from registration. The EPA will take action against companies that make such claims. Additionally, the EPA must also approve the wording of health-related claims for products that have undergone complete evaluation and registration under FIFRA⁴⁷.

⁴⁵ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

⁴⁶ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

⁴⁷ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

Importantly, however, in the United States, under a “Treated Articles Exemption” of FIFRA, companies can avoid a lengthy pesticide registration process if they refrain from making explicit or implicit health benefit claims about the antimicrobial product and make clear to customers that the biocide if it is mentioned at all, is solely for the protection of the treated article.^{48,49} As a result, products containing biocides that are exempted under this provision do not need to be evaluated for human health or environmental impacts, nor do they need to be evaluated for efficacy in reducing surface microbial load and potential for the article to serve as a source or reservoir for pathogens responsible for HAIs.

Antimicrobials that are added to a product to preserve the material are often not identified to distributors or consumers, and in such cases, their presence is unknown. However, the antimicrobial is identified and marketed for contributing stain- or odor-control properties to the product in some cases. In addition, if a treated article exemption is claimed under FIFRA, the manufacturer is prohibited from making any health-related statements about the product. However, despite these marketing limitations, customers often assume that if microorganisms are less likely to grow on the surface of a product, people touching the surface will be less likely to contact them. It seems likely that this assumption⁵¹ underlies much of the growing consumer interest in products with antimicrobial properties⁵⁰.

The FDA regulates medical devices and antimicrobials added to medical devices to reduce infection risk.⁵² These will not be further considered in this paper. The FDA also regulates

⁴⁸ See <http://www.epa.gov/pesticides/factsheets/treatart.htm> accessed August 29, 2015

⁴⁹ <http://www2.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2014-04/documents/pr2000-1.pdf>

⁵⁰ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

Dow. Microbial Control. Growing consumer interest in personal and family wellness creates potential growth opportunities for sales of clothing, footwear, and home products treated with next-generation antimicrobials.

<http://www.dow.com/microbial/news/2013/20130910a.htm>

⁵² <http://www.fda.gov/RegulatoryInformation/Guidances/ucm071380.htm>

chemical sterilants and high-level disinfectants described above and used for processing semicritical devices⁵³.

ANTIMICROBIALS IN HOSPITAL FURNISHINGS

According to guidelines, integrated efforts involving surveillance, rigorous hand hygiene, and cleaning and disinfection are proven methods for preventing and controlling HAIs. However, strict adherence to guidelines at all times is challenging, and some facilities are looking at newer technologies to see if they add value to ongoing efforts. Among them is the addition of antimicrobial⁵⁴ to medical devices that may contact blood or mucous membranes and furnishings and building products with surfaces (such as handrails, corner guards, walls) that may become contaminated with pathogens and aid infectious disease transmission. Surfaces on products and materials in patient care areas are of particular interest because they can provide a reservoir for pathogens along the transmission pathway from one person to another⁵⁵.

ANTIMICROBIAL COATINGS AND SURFACE TECHNOLOGIES WITH SILVER BIOCIDES

Being a natural antimicrobial ingredient, silver has been used by wound healing professionals for many years, primarily due to its scientifically proven antimicrobial efficacy. Unfortunately, many Americans invaded the country at birth when to prevent silver nitrate from entering the country.

As a result, medicine recognized the silver owner of the role of an antimicrobial agent.

Prophylactic use of silver, a non-toxic, identified antimicrobial agent, is used primarily when the risk of infection is present or suspected - active mixed composition of various bacteria and fungi. At the same time, silver has a very high tendency to develop skin diseases, and the bacterium rarely develops into persistent manifestations. In addition, in warm environments,

⁵³ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

⁵⁴ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

⁵⁵ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

silver ions are highly "bioreactive" - meaning they are eager to attach to other traits-binding to proteins inside and outside bacterial cell membranes. This is the suppression of respiration and cell reproduction.

Silver is used to killing bacteria by removing any microorganisms that "land" on it. Dealing with silver is by ionization since releasing electrons from silver suffocates any microorganisms that come into contact with it—the warmer and wetter the environment. Therefore, where the bacteria grow, the stronger they manifest themselves.

Silver's broad-spectrum antimicrobial properties have long been recognized and used in water and air purification, food production, cosmetics, medical applications, textiles, clothing, and many household products.^{56'57} Global production of textiles with antimicrobial properties, including added silver, was estimated at 100,000 tons in 2000, with rapid annual growth.^{58'59} Silver-containing preparations prevent infections in burns, traumatic wounds, and diabetic ulcers in healthcare. Urinary and vascular catheters and other devices are sometimes impregnated with silver compounds to reduce the risk of infection. Various technologies employ metallic silver, silver salts, silver-polymer composites, silver-impregnated zeolites (microporous, aluminosilicate minerals commonly used as commercial adsorbents and catalysts), or silver nanoparticles (clusters of silver atoms⁶⁰, ions with at least one dimension measuring 1-100 nm).

⁵⁶ Marambio-Jones C, Hoek E. A review of the antibacterial effects of silver nanomaterials and potential implications for human health and the environment. *J Nanopart Res* 2010; 12: 1531–1551.

⁵⁷ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

⁵⁸ Gao, Y., Cranston, R. Recent advances in antimicrobial treatments of textiles. *Text Res J.* 2008; 78, 60–72.

⁵⁹ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

⁶⁰ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

Concentrations of silver in textiles can vary widely from 2-3000 mg/kg (ppm).^{61'62'63} Silver can be effective against various microorganisms, including gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, fungi, viruses, yeast, and algae, depending on how it is deployed.⁶⁴

Silver-containing environmental surfaces and textiles in health care settings are increasingly promoted as products that may help reduce HAIs by reducing microbial loads as demonstrated in laboratory studies or environmental microbiological testing.^{65'66'67}

7. DESIGNING INTELLIGENT INTERIORS: CLEANER BY DESIGN

Bea Spolidoro, principal at FisherARCHitecture of Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, talks about the impact our home and work environments have on our physical and psychological health⁶⁸. She argues that they, as architects, must be smart about the choice of materials for each project and that they can learn a lot from the food industry for hospital design.

It is also essential to give cleaning and disinfection. Cleaning removes dirt, dust, oils, and other contaminants. Disinfection uses chemical solutions to mix contaminants such as bacteria, viruses, mold, and fungi. Many believe the best approach is a two-step process: first clean with

⁶¹ Voelker D, Schlich K, Hohndorf L, Koch W, et al. approach on environmental risk assessment of nanosilver released from textiles. *Environ Res.* 2015; 140:661-672.

⁶² Lorenz C, Windler L, von Goetz N, Lehman R, et al. Characterization of silver release from commercially available functional (nano)textiles. *Chemosphere.* 2012; 89(7):817-824.

⁶³ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

⁶⁴ Maillard J, Hartemann P. Silver as an antimicrobial: facts and gaps in knowledge *Crit Rev Microbiol.* 2013; 39(4):373- 383.

⁶⁵ Markarian J. Antimicrobials find new healthcare applications. *Plastics Additives Compounding.* Jan/Feb 2009.

⁶⁶ Simoncic B, Klemencic D. Preparation and performance of silver as an antimicrobial agent for textiles: A review. *Textile Research J.* 0040517515586157

⁶⁷ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

⁶⁸ An Architect's Tips For A 'Healthy' Home Design - Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/reginacole/2020/05/28/how-architecture-can-defend-us-from-germs-bacteria-and-viruses-like-covid-19/>

soap and water, let this solution do its job, and then apply disinfectants in a “second pass.” This “double whammy” is that soap and disinfectants have the best effect on germs.

When designing a space, the most important thing is to make any cleaning process easier: hard-to-reach places or tight corners, reduce the number of seams on countertops, and keep in mind that nothing can easily fall behind built-in furniture. In addition, avoid overly complex structures in production that are often touched, such as door handles, handles, buttons, controls, railings, and handrails: a flat, smooth surface is easy to clean.

It is also recommended to select materials available for clean and nonporous surfaces. For example, granite and other natural stone surfaces are porous and can be absorbed by moisture, water particles, and microbial spores. Surfaces such as steel, quartz, or Corian are nonporous and quickly disinfected. On the other hand, porous materials such as carpets, textiles, upholstery, wallpaper for curtains, linen, bedding, and curtains require care when cleaning, especially against dust mites, which can cause allergies.

One more thing to add to his advice: We do not need to sacrifice aesthetics to gain cleanability.

EXTENDING THE USE OF SILVER-CONTAINING BIOCIDES IN ARFEN PRODUCTS

Silver, copper, and zinc demonstrate significant antimicrobial activity with a broad therapeutic index. Of the three, silver is the least cytotoxic⁶⁹ and the most potent against bacteria, roughly ten times as potent as copper. The antimicrobial effect of zinc is perhaps three orders of magnitude weaker than that of silver.

Silver has a long history of use as an antimicrobial, with applications in water storage dating to the 5th century BC. Today silver is used regularly in water filtration media to control bacteria growth and prevent fouling of pipes and machinery due to the growth of biofilms⁷⁰. In addition, silver compounds have long been used to prevent ophthalmia neonatorum due to *Neisseria*

⁶⁹ Williams RL, et al., *The Biocompatibility of Silver*, Critical Reviews in Biocompatibility, 1989, 5:221-243

⁷⁰ Transmission Of SARS And Other Pathogens Novel https://www.cheeverspecialty.com/documents/novel_antimicrobial.pdf

gonorrhoeae.⁷¹ Silver sulfadiazine creams have been widely accepted in burn therapy since the 1960s.⁷²⁷³ Silver-eluting urinary catheters have been shown to reduce the incidence of catheter-associated infection.⁷⁴ Silver has demonstrated antiviral activity against herpes simplex, vaccinia, influenza A and pseudorabies viruses in water.⁷⁵ Silver also has antifungal activity,⁷⁶ and has demonstrated a clinically significant ability to inhibit colonization of soft denture materials with *Candida albicans*.⁷⁷ Many other silver-containing substances are used in medicine.⁷⁸⁷⁹

Ionic silver is a broad spectrum antimicrobial to which bacteria show a low propensity to develop resistance.⁸⁰ Silver has been found to interfere with sulfhydryl groups on enzymes involved with metabolism and proteins in the tissue structure of a microorganism. In addition, silver inhibits replication by binding to and denaturing bacterial DNA and RNA⁸¹⁸²⁸³ suggesting

⁷¹ Bonilla HF, et al., Long term survival of vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecium* on a contaminated surface. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol.* 1995;17:770-771

⁷² Landsdown ABG, Silver I: Antibacterial Properties and Mechanism of Action, *Journal of Wound Care*, 2002, 11:125-130

⁷³ Transmission Of SARS And Other Pathogens Novel https://www.cheeverspecialty.com/documents/novel_antimicrobial.pdf

⁷⁴ Saint, S et al., The potential Clinical and Economic Benefits of Silver Alloy Urinary Catheters in Preventing Urinary Tract Infection, *Arch Intern Med.*, 2000, 160:2670-2675

⁷⁵ Grashoff GJ and King RO, Silver in Medical Applications, in *Concise Encyclopedia of Medical and Dental Materials*. Ed, Williams, D, MIT Press 1992, 321-326

⁷⁶ Berger TJ, et al., Antifungal Properties of Electrically Generated Metallic Ions, *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 1976;10:856-860

⁷⁷ Nikawa H, et al., Antifungal Effect of Zeolite-incorporated tissue conditioner against *Candida albicans* Growth and/or Acid Production, *J Oral Rehab.*, 1997, 24:350-357

⁷⁸ Medical Quality, FDA, & EPA Approved Silver Products; Silvermedicine.org website; September 27, 2004; <http://www.silvermedicine.org/medical-products-silver.html>

⁷⁹ Transmission Of SARS And Other Pathogens Novel https://www.cheeverspecialty.com/documents/novel_antimicrobial.pdf

⁸⁰ Survival of pseudorabies virus in the presence of selected diluents and fomites. Schoenbaum MA, Freund JD, Beran GW. *J Am Vet Med Assoc.* 1991 Apr 15;198(8):1393-7.

⁸¹ Wysor MS, and Zollinhofer, RE, On the mode of action of silver sulphadiazine, *Path Microbiol*, 1972, 38:296- 308

⁸² Modak, SM, Binding of silver sulfadiazine to the cellular components of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Biochemical Pharmacology*, 1973;22:2391-2404

⁸³ Model of the crystal structure of zeolite 4A. The blue https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Model-of-the-crystal-structure-of-zeolite-4A-The-blue-spheres-represent-silver-ions_fig2_265224065

a possible mechanism for inactivation of viruses. The observed strong antimicrobial efficacy of silver ions even at low concentrations is attributed to a strong tendency for bacteria to collect and concentrate silver⁸⁴.

Although silver is an effective antimicrobial, effective deployment requires the proper ionic species at the right concentration.

At least one durable, long-lasting, readily-engineered silver delivery mechanism is readily available in zeolites and ionpure, porous particles made from a particular formulation of inert aluminosilicate. Silver biocides are heat-stable and provide an effective and consistent delivery mechanism for inorganic antimicrobial agents while withstanding most industrial processes, including those used to prepare and apply surface coatings and manufacture and extrusion plastics⁸⁵.

Figure 2. How ionpure silver works.

With the presence of moisture, IONPURE releases a few Ag ions gradually. Ag⁸⁶ ions can strongly bind to cellular enzymes of microbes and inhibit the enzyme activity of cell walls,

⁸⁴ Model of the crystal structure of zeolite 4A. The blue https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Model-of-the-crystal-structure-of-zeolite-4A-The-blue-spheres-represent-silver-ions_fig2_265224065

⁸⁵ Model of the crystal structure of zeolite 4A. The blue https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Model-of-the-crystal-structure-of-zeolite-4A-The-blue-spheres-represent-silver-ions_fig2_265224065

⁸⁶ IONPURE - Microkiller® Antimicrobial - Antimicrobial Agent http://sr-business.com/en/products_Show.asp?ProductID=384

membrane, and nucleic acids. As microbes are charged with minus on their surface, Ag ions that have plus are drawn toward microbes and disturb their electric balance. So that microbes are burst their cell wall and extinguished⁸⁷.

Otherwise, as Ag ions are taken into microbes, they react and bond to the cellular enzyme microbes. This inhibits enzyme activity and multiplication of microbes, thus extinguishing the microbes.⁸⁸

IONPURE Silver in ARFEN products are recognized as approved by FIFRA, EPA, FDA, NSF.

SILVER BIOCIDES AND HUMAN SARS-COV VIRUS

Although silver biocides have been previously shown to be effective against other coronaviruses, their effectiveness against SARS-CoV, the etiologic agent of SARS, has been studied. Nevertheless, it obeys the same biological laws, and silver biocides in the composition of materials, as studies show, significantly reduce the spread of diseases.

PURE is an antimicrobial agent used in plastics and silicone. PURE is an inorganic, soluble glass containing antimicrobial metal ions that are effective against 99.9% of many microorganisms, including Methicillin-resistant microorganisms. The PURE inorganic silver-ion antimicrobial agent is a product of ISHIZUKA GLASS CO., LTD. of Japan, registered to EPA & FDA (USA).

As the best effective inorganic antibacterial material, IONPURE comprises silver ion and transparent mesh structure glass as a carrier. The silver ion provides an antibacterial effect of over 99.9% against very wide microorganisms, including Methicillin-resistant microorganisms, at a very low dosage of 0.3%. Adding IONPURE will bring minimal effect to the transparency & color of plastic-like PS, ABS. Bacteria will not consume PURE, so it lasts almost life long as the plastic product. So it is widely used for all plastics⁸⁹, textiles, food packages, toys, and paintings.

⁸⁷ IONPURE - Microkiller® Antimicrobial - Antimicrobial Agent http://sr-business.com/en/products_Show.asp?ProductID=384

⁸⁸ <https://www.ishizuka.co.jp/english/material/antimicrobial/#date01>

⁸⁹ IONPURE silver ion antimicrobial EPA FDA registered http://www.trinionchem.com/sdp/330645/4/pd-1416365/5293466/IONPURE_silver_ion_antimicrobial_EPA_FDA_registere.html

Silver ion is slowly released at a controlled speed from the glass mesh to kill bacteria and inhibit the growth of microorganisms. The antimicrobial effect will not be influenced or reduced by light or heat⁹⁰.

Compared with other silver-ion antimicrobial materials, IONPURE possesses the advantages:

*Various designs for different kinds of plastic.

*Very low dosage (0.3%) is adequate to achieve a very high effect.

*Keeps high transparency of plastic like PP, PC, ABS.

*With stable quality, IONPURE releases silver⁹¹ ions at a stable speed (tested through washing and boiling in water), so it kills bacteria steadily and permanently.

*Safe & environment protective (LD50>2000mg/kg), EPA & FDA registered.

*Stable under processing temperature 500C, so IONPURE is good for all plastic processes of molding & intrusion.⁹²⁹³

⁹⁰ IONPURE silver ion antimicrobial EPA FDA registered http://www.trinionchem.com/sdp/330645/4/pd-1416365/5293466/IONPURE_silver_ion_antimicrobial_EPA_FDA_registere.html

⁹¹ IONPURE silver ion antimicrobial EPA FDA registered http://www.trinionchem.com/sdp/330645/4/pd-1416365/5293466/IONPURE_silver_ion_antimicrobial_EPA_FDA_registere.html

⁹² http://www.trinionchem.com/sdp/330645/4/pd-1416365/5293466-710205/IONPURE_silver_ion_antimicrobial_EPA_FDA_registere.html

⁹³ <https://www.ishizuka.co.jp/english/material/antimicrobial/>

WG 42-1 Handrail System

WG 42-1 can be used for holding purposes in hospital corridors and common areas, in staircase openings. With its color alternatives, warm decorative texture and end parts which is not available in any other railing, it can be used as railing systems in schools, hotels, malls, business centers and houses. The profile length is 4 meters and produced in 32 different colors.

CONCLUSIONS

Surface biocontamination is a problem that develops with community-acquired and hospital-acquired infections due to the episodic transmission of the disease through fomites and the formation of fomite reservoirs.

The faster occurrence of pathogen dieback at the surface can significantly reduce the amount of time that a fomite reservoir causes transfer and reduce the rate of emergence of a population of pathogens available for transmission to a susceptible host.

An initial experimental study of SARS inactivation⁹⁴ with an antimicrobial biocide powder showed inactivation in bulk suspension within two hours.

Craig Feed, in his research "Novel Antimicrobial Surface Coatings And The Potential For Reduced Fomite Transmission Of SARS And Other Pathogens," investigates that the faster occurrence of pathogen dieback at the surface can reduce the time that a reservoir of fomites causes transmission and can also reduce the rate of emergence of a pathogen population available to a susceptible host.⁹⁵

⁹⁴ Transmission Of SARS And Other Pathogens Novel https://www.cheeverspecialty.com/documents/novel_antimicrobial.pdf

⁹⁵ Novel Antimicrobial Surface Coatings And The Potential For Reduced Fomite Transmission Of SARS And Other Pathogens Craig Feied

The World Health Organization (WHO) Consensus document on the epidemiology of SARS also presents evidence implicating⁹⁶ fomite transmission.

Furthermore, hospital locations such as the emergency department or the intensive care unit can be overloaded with very sick patients around the clock, making regular disinfection impractical. Where constant manual disinfection is impractical, surfaces are selected, disinfections disappear, and persistent manifestations appear or appear externally. Using ARFEN products as one part of the puzzle can help reduce SARS-Cov viruses, and other types of virus activities are critical.

Figure 3: Survival effect on accumulation on the average surface versus antimicrobial surface.

Survival times are typical of experimentally determining survival times observed for common pathogenic organisms on treated and untreated surfaces. Episodes of cross-contamination can occur in a short time, and thus, unless infection on the surface is complete and recurrent, it will

⁹⁶

not prevent all episodes of cross-infection. However, the death of pathogens does not have to be complete isolation to reduce infection transmission. Decrease in clinical transmission if total fomite reservoir activity time is reduced.

Thus, survival on the Earth's surface is a fomite collection reservoir, a recognized goal of preventing the spread of disease.⁹⁷

Effective routine chemical disinfection is difficult because solid chemical solutions must be applied correctly and left in contact with surfaces for prolonged periods. In addition, many materials are not amenable to such treatments, and many clinical environments do not accommodate them easily.

Novel surface coatings offer the potential for self-decontamination through the controlled release of antimicrobial metal ions by non-toxic industrial coatings that can be applied to and incorporated within many different types of surfaces and materials⁹⁸ like ionpure silver in ARFEN wall protection and handrail products.

The faster surface die-off of pathogens on a surface can significantly reduce the amount of time that a fomites reservoir is capable of transmitting disease and can also reduce the average surface population of pathogens available for transmission to a susceptible host⁹⁹.

8. PRODUCT AND MATERIAL OPTIONS FOR CLEANER BUILDINGS WITH IONPURE SILVER

Extruded plastic applications:

- Wall Cladding (rigid sheet wall protection)
- Profile products:
 - o Handrail wall guard
 - o Corner guards

⁹⁷ Novak KD, Kowalski RP, Karenchak LM, Gordon YJ: Chlamydia trachomatis can be transmitted by a nonporous plastic surface in vitro. Cornea. 1995 Sep;14(5):523-6.

⁹⁸ Transmission Of SARS And Other Pathogens Novel https://www.cheeverspecialty.com/documents/novel_antimicrobial.pdf

⁹⁹ Transmission Of SARS And Other Pathogens Novel https://www.cheeverspecialty.com/documents/novel_antimicrobial.pdf

- o Chair rail wall guard
- o Door kickplates

ANTIMICROBIAL TECHNOLOGIES DESIGNATED FOR HANDRAILS

One option for dealing with germs is spraying against built-in antimicrobial technologies. Unfortunately, as the name suggests, spray technologies are reasonably easy to use and scarce but have a limited lifespan - most manufacturers claim effectiveness from 90 days to 1 year, which inevitably repeats the application. Moreover, of course, this assumes proper and complete application upon installation.

Embedded technologies are incorporated during manufacturing and are mixed in and bonded with the substrate material, such as the cover on a handrail. As a result, it has a slight cost premium over standard materials but benefits from a longer functional life.

Application of embedded IONPURE silver that ARFEN uses in handrail (and ARFEN all protection systems) grip surfaces reduces the number of microbes on the surface, as we showed above.

WALL CLADDING SYSTEM FOR PRODUCTION ENVIRONMENTS

Hygienic Wall Cladding is Industrial-strength, non-fiberglass reinforced panels that offer high impact resistance and are thermally stable to handle the humidity and heat fluctuations. Field production is standard because the panel is easy to cut and not subject to the harmful dust associated with FRP fabrication.

The system offers material flexibility and outstanding design. Architects and building owners combine a wall base with a box wall panel that comes close to their imagination, including Hygienic Wall Cladding and Solid Surface Wall Cladding.

This system includes applications in laboratories, pharmaceutical manufacturing, clean rooms, food processing plants and food kitchens, hospital manufacturing, university canteens, and restaurants.

Since a solid surface is non-nutritive, it does not promote the growth of mold and mildew and resists bacterial growth. In addition, incorporating active antimicrobials into the hard surface itself can reduce allergenic odors.

It is an excellent and reliable solution for operating theaters and other protective environments.

The material benefits of a solid surface are:

- Nonporous,
- Extremely durable -- long lifecycle,
- Many colors and particulate combinations are available.

WG 1004 GREEN VINYL PLATE

ARFEN

ARFEN VINYL PLATE

➤ WG1004

1000mm

WG 1004 Vinyl Plate
 WG 1004 Plate system is 1000 mm wide. It protects and preserves building interior walls against impacts and wears. These economic plates are installed quickly and simply. They are produced in 32 different colours and 3 meters length.

APPLICATIONS

WG1004

CONCLUSION

As we wrap up, we hope we have gained a good and broader perspective of "the new normal" when keeping facilities cleaner. Everyone is stepping up their role, from architects, items now assembled as part of their production, to facility owners and staff. As a result, items will need to be cleaned frequently with more potent disinfectants.

Furthermore, we have shown that there are materials that can stand up to these harsher cleaning routines and incorporate active antimicrobials that help keep microbes in check.

Manufacturers of healthcare furnishings have been developing new products with antimicrobial properties to protect materials from degradation for aesthetic reasons and reduce microbial burdens on product surfaces, anticipating that this may help reduce the risk of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs). Industry experts predict hospitals will continue to increase purchases of products containing antimicrobials. Antimicrobial use in other consumer products, including items for food production and storage, personal care, clothing, household goods, and building materials, is also increasing. These uses collectively add to the potential for the general population and environmental exposures¹⁰⁰.

Healthcare-associated infections have always been a formidable challenge in hospitals and are significant causes of morbidity and mortality today. Healthcare-associated infections can prolong the length of hospital stays, resulting in readmission after discharge and increasing costs to individuals, families, and communities. Moreover, under the Affordable Care Act provisions, preventable readmissions can result in a financial penalty in reimbursement for all Medicare patients at that hospital. This has driven an interest in developing new strategies to reduce HAIs¹⁰¹.

ARFEN pays excellent attention to the composition and components of its materials. That is why the use of silver ions by a Japanese company in the composition of wall protection materials gives such unique features and advantages on the market. However, is it possible to evaluate the economic impact of using such materials in order to find out how many lives can

¹⁰⁰ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

¹⁰¹ Antimicrobials in Hospital Furnishings - Willis. https://www.4willis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Antimicrobials-Report-2016_1.pdf

be saved by reducing the spread of diseases transmitted through the surfaces of handrails and walls? Yes, it is possible and evident that using materials with active antimicrobial properties provides significant benefits to society. Nevertheless, do we need to evaluate the value of human life, or should we just start applying best practices?

We use ionpure silver because it is approved by FIFRA, EPA, FDA, and NSF. Impure silver is an inorganic, soluble glass containing antimicrobial metal ions effective against 99.9% of many microorganisms.

We believe and adhere to the view that the health care system is made up of small and large pieces, and every detail in human health care is essential. Therefore, using materials with active antibacterial properties that counteract the spread of known SARS and other types of microorganisms is essential. Moreover, the systematic and planned use of such materials will significantly reduce the burden on the healthcare system while improving the quality of life¹⁰² of people.

¹⁰² What is Value Based Care in Healthcare?. <https://www.vytalizehealth.com/post/vytalize-health-partners-with-glucose-guards-to-improve-the-quality-of-care-for-patients-while-reducing-healthcare-costs>

PART 2: APPROACHES TO REDUCE THE AMOUNT OF PATIENT-FALL INJURIES

1. INTRODUCTION

Each year, between 700,000 and 1 million patients fall in the hospital. That rivals the number of patients who contract a¹⁰³ healthcare-associated infection (HAI). Of those patient falls, 11,000 results in a fatality, and 30-35% result in injuries. Therefore, extended stays to treat fall injuries mean bottom-line impacts for the hospital.

The increasing focus of government agencies and healthcare industry associations is being brought to bear on reducing what could almost be called the epidemic of slips and falls.

Certainly, slip-fall prevention takes a multi-faceted approach¹⁰⁴. However, this white paper offers several design options that show promise in the fight against slip-fall injuries.

2. FIRST, DO NO HARM.

Hippocrates' command is well known to health professionals, and it certainly is first and foremost in their hearts and minds. So naturally, therefore, when folks come to the hospital for care and treatment – and end up in worse conditions – it weighs heavily on the individual and collective consciousness of the healthcare provider community.

The vexing problem of healthcare-associated infections has been exhaustively covered by the media and numerous academic journal articles. Nevertheless, hundreds of thousands of Americans enter the hospital each year and contract pernicious and sometimes fatal infections from bacteria that have grown increasingly immune to the most potent medicines.

What may be surprising to many is the equally high incidence of another type of harm happening to inpatients admitted to the hospital. However, again, patient falls statistically rival HAIs in their incidence rates and impact patients' physical health and a hospital's finances.

¹⁰³ Nano-Grip The Safe Floor Solution | Safety Through Science <https://nanogrip.wordpress.com/page/2/>

¹⁰⁴ Nano-Grip The Safe Floor Solution | Safety Through Science <https://nanogrip.wordpress.com/page/2/>

The patient-fall statistics are not pretty.

The following infographic outlines the breadth and severe impacts of in-hospital falls:

Figure 4. Graphic courtesy Joint Commission Center for Transforming Healthcare

Although research has suggested that approximately one-third of the 700 000 to 1 million patient falls in US hospitals could be prevented, reducing falls with injuries is a persistent patient safety challenge. Falls can result in patient injury and death and place an increased economic

burden on patients and the health care system¹⁰⁵. More extended hospital stays and additional treatment necessary after falls contribute to a 61% increase in inpatient care costs, five although the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services limits reimbursement for falls that result in injuries such as fractures, dislocations, and intracranial injuries¹⁰⁶. Falls have been identified by the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services as a healthcare-acquired condition —an event that is preventable and should not occur¹⁰⁷. To reduce the risk of falls, hospitals have traditionally engaged in efforts focused on creating safe environments and educating nursing and other staff about falls and injury prevention. Hospitals have also relied on measuring rates of falls to identify opportunities for improvement. Despite these widespread and long-term efforts, there are 2.3 to 7 falls per 1000 patient days, and many hospitals continue to struggle with finding reliable methods for reducing the risk of patient falls.¹⁰⁸¹⁰⁹

3. FALLS HURT STAFF, TOO

The well-prepared hospital or skilled nursing facility trains staff to, where and when possible, "help" a patient fall. This means staff physically intervenes to hopefully allow the patient to have a softer landing and avoid serious head or limb injury from striking fixtures (sinks, toilets).

The number of hospital staff injured while assisting falling patients is not readily visible in all the statistics. For example, the nationwide numbers of strained backs, sprained ankles, and broken bones of nurses and caregivers injured in physical-fall interventions are elusive, as are the costs of staff medical claims and lost workdays.

¹⁰⁵ [PDF] A New Approach to Preventing Falls With Injuries <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-New-Approach-to-Preventing-Falls-With-Injuries-DuPree-Fritz-Campiz/7e7094f6dadf94a2c37411eb3524224b0230975b>

¹⁰⁶ [PDF] Preventing falls and fall-related injuries in health <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Preventing-falls-and-fall-related-injuries-in-care/e092c77011724a5769642c4341a57462e7428cf4>

¹⁰⁷ MSN-FP6212 Executive Summary.docx - Running head <https://www.coursehero.com/file/52899513/MSN-FP6212-Executive-Summarydocx/>

¹⁰⁸ https://www.centerfortransforminghealthcare.org/-/media/cthd/documents/what-we-offer/a_new_approach_to_preventing_falls_with_injuries.pdf

¹⁰⁹ https://www.jointcommission.org/-/media/tjc/documents/resources/patient-safety-topics/sentinel-event/sea_55_falls_4_26_16.pdf

Also, untracked are the psychological impacts on staff when a patient falls. As humans, and more so as caregivers, seeing a patient harmed while in their care takes an often hidden toll. "Devastating" was the word used to describe the death of a 90-year-old woman from a fall-related traumatic brain injury at a small hospital in Great Barrington, Mass¹¹⁰.

We would be naïve to deny patient falls' physical and emotional impacts on staff.

4. ENTER THE LAWYERS

To think that the financial "meter" stops running once the post-fall injured patient is discharged. America's litigious culture means lawsuits for negligence are a fact of life. A case in Syracuse, NY, is illustrative:

An 88-year-old man died following a fall at Syracuse medical facility. His wife filed suit, claiming her husband was not adequately monitored despite a history of falling. In addition, as alleged in the filing, despite several indicators of high fall risk, the patient was not issued an orange bracelet to indicate that risk, even though that was the hospital's policy. The suit also alleged the nurse involved was inadequately trained in fall prevention and failed to provide adequate assistance during a trip to the bathroom, during which the patient fell.¹¹¹

So hospitals need to reduce the out-of-pocket cost to treat fall injuries occurring to the admitted patient, but they also must reduce the potential for litigation.

5. FALLS PREVENTION INTERVENTIONS IN THE MEDICARE POPULATION

Falls are a significant health problem among older adults in the United States. One in every three people over the age of 65 years living in the community falls each year, and this proportion increases to one in two by the age of 80 years.

¹¹⁰ <http://www.wbur.org/2009/08/25/falling-down>

¹¹¹ https://www.syracuse.com/news/2013/01/st_josephs_hospital_faces_laws.html

Fall-related injuries in older adults often reduce mobility and independence and are often severe enough to result in hospitalization and an increased risk of premature death.⁴ Studies among older persons in the community have found that about 10 percent of the fallers have fall-related severe injuries, including fractures, joint dislocations, or severe head injuries. Falling has also been associated with subsequent admission to a nursing home.¹¹²

The costs of healthcare associated with fall-related injuries and fractures, including hip fractures, are staggering. The total direct cost of all fall injuries in older adults in 1994 was \$20.2 billion and is estimated to reach \$32.4 billion by 2020. Medicare costs for hip fractures were estimated in 1991 to be \$2.9 billion¹¹³. With an aging population and many hip fractures, these cost estimates will rise to \$240 billion by 2040.

The prevention of falls is an important issue if it can prevent significant declines in function and independence and the associated increase in costs of complications. The significant risk factors for falling are diverse, and many of them are potentially modifiable, such as balance impairment, muscle weakness, polypharmacy, and environmental hazards. However, the interventions designed to address these risk factors share the same diversity. Likewise, the evidence for the effectiveness of a single intervention in preventing falls has been inadequate. Since the risk of falling appears to increase with the number of risk factors, multifactorial interventions have been suggested as the most effective strategy to reduce falls.^{114'115'116'117}

¹¹² Falls Prevention Interventions in the Medicare Population. <https://www.cms.gov/Medicare/Prevention/PrevntionGenInfo/Downloads/Falls-Evidence-Report.pdf>

¹¹³ Falls Prevention Interventions in the Medicare Population. <https://www.cms.gov/Medicare/Prevention/PrevntionGenInfo/Downloads/Falls-Evidence-Report.pdf>

¹¹⁴ <https://www.cms.gov/Medicare/Prevention/PrevntionGenInfo/Downloads/Falls-Evidence-Report.pdf>

¹¹⁵ <https://www.jointcommission.org/-/media/tjc/documents/resources/speak-up/speak-ups/to-prevent-falls/speak-up-falls-85-x-11.pdf>

¹¹⁶ Falls Prevention Interventions in the Medicare Population. <https://www.cms.gov/Medicare/Prevention/PrevntionGenInfo/Downloads/Falls-Evidence-Report.pdf>

¹¹⁷ Fall Prevention Certification Program - HIPAA Compliance <https://epiconferences.com/fall-prevention-certification-program/>

6. MEDICARE USES FUNDING “STICK” TO REVERSE A BAD TREND

As it did in an attempt to turn the tide in HAI rates and other medical errors, the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) eliminated reimbursements for fall-injury treatments. The ripple effect moved from Medicare at the federal level to state Medicare programs and through to the country's largest private insurers. As one of the so-called Medicare "Never Events," the costs of treating hospital fall injuries must be paid out of the hospitals' coffers.

The logic applied is like an auto mechanic breaking our windshield while fixing our engine – the mechanic would never get away with billing us to fix the windshield. So Medicare told providers, "You 'broke it'... you pay to fix it." The step was seen as a symbolic line in the sand and put healthcare providers and systems on notice to pay closer attention to medical errors and work to reduce patient harm.

With HAIs, one study in the *New England Journal of Medicine*¹¹⁸ reports that the CMS "penalty" approach to affect change has had little or no effect on catheter-associated infection rates. By extension, one would hope that eliminating Medicare payments for preventable falls would have some effect and that rates of fall incidents and resulting injuries would drop. The jury is still out.

7. SO, WHAT CAN BE DONE?

Most of the academic literature on preventing patient falls seems to coalesce around several vital approaches, which are listed and briefly fleshed out here as follows¹¹⁹:

Identifying patients with higher fall risk – using assessment tools to flag conditions that may lead to more significant potential to fall – for example, poor vision; low blood pressure; under opiates, sedatives, or other pain meds; debility in the lower limbs.

¹¹⁸ https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMsa1202419?query=featured_home&&

¹¹⁹ <https://www.flexmonitoring.org>, https://www.flexmonitoring.org/sites/flexmonitoring.umn.edu/files/media/policybrief24_falls-prevention.pdf

Staff Education – training staff to recognize indicators of and monitor fall-susceptible patients. Patient Education – educating the patient on getting up and moving safely and when to ring for assistance versus "freelancing" a trip to the toilet.

Environmental Risks – eliminating hazards like slippery floors, cluttered pathways, and wheeled furniture.

Staff Assistance – scheduling staff rounds for more frequent visits to assist with trips to the bathroom.

Family Assistance – enlisting and educating visiting family members to help the patient when they go mobile.

Organizational Factors – creating well-crafted policies and procedures that support staff; supplying adequate funding for items like patient-movement alarms; providing sufficient coverage by well-trained staff.

Patient Safety Culture – infusing a cross-organizational mindset to keep patients safe, documenting and correcting errors, taking immediate corrective action, and making continuous improvements.

8. JOINT COMMISSION FALL PREVENTION PROJECT SHOWS PROMISE

The Joint Commission Center for Transforming Healthcare recently¹²⁰ concluded a three-year pilot project by seven hospitals that showed some dramatic results in reducing falls with injuries. From the Center's news release¹²¹:

New measurement systems and solutions developed by the Joint Commission Center for Transforming Healthcare Preventing Falls with Injury as part of a project to reduce the incidence of diseases with injuries, the likelihood of reducing the incidence of patients by 35 percent, and the number of patients who received cases by 62 percent.

¹²⁰ Perfecting the basics helps healthcare fight the <https://www.centerfortransforminghealthcare.org/press-room/news/2020/03/perfecting-the-basics-helps-healthcare-fight-the-unexpected/>

¹²¹ <https://www.centerfortransforminghealthcare.org/-/media/cthd/documents/what-we-offer/preventing-falls-tst-fact-sheet-8-15.pdf>

Specifics on each funding round, including the amounts, funding sources, and short-listed investors.

If the approach is a 200-bed hospital, the number of patients who get severe injuries falling can be reduced from 117 to 45, likely saving about \$1 million annually in falls mitigation measures. Similarly, a 400-bed hospital could reduce 133 people's injury falls and calculate an annual savings of \$1.9 million.

The hospitals that worked on this project ranged from a 178-bed community hospital to a 1,700-bed academic medical center¹²². All organizations use Robust Process Improvement (RPI®) to identify causes and develop solutions to prevent patient falls. RPI is a fact-based, systematic, and data-driven problem-solving methodology¹²³ that incorporates tools and concepts from Lean, Six Sigma, and change management.

The pilot group is to be commended. From the quoted "... Lean, Six Sigma and change management" statement, one can surmise that many operational and procedural aspects were studied and will be targeted for improvement. However, we will have to wait for a more-encompassing final report and the touted TST® to see what was done to achieve the results.

9. A CAUTIONARY TALE FROM THE FIGHT AGAINST HAIS

We began this paper speaking of the multi-disciplinary approach that must be used to prevent falls. However, if we have realized one thing about the HAI "superbugs" haunting hospitals' patient spaces, there is no "silver bullet" solution that will eradicate healthcare-associated infections.

For instance, hand washing by healthcare workers is all the rage. However, the rate of infection and cross-contamination cannot consistently be reduced for long periods, in part because humans are, well, human. They get lazy or under stress and forget to scrub their

¹²² An instructive video about using the TST is available on https://www.centerfortransforminghealthcare.org/-/media/CTH/Documents/What-We-Offer/TST_brochure.pdf

¹²³ An instructive video about using the TST is available on https://www.centerfortransforminghealthcare.org/-/media/CTH/Documents/What-We-Offer/TST_brochure.pdf

hands before moving to the next patient. It indicates that HAI transmission can be an elusive process that escapes the wariest of healthcare practitioners.

We would offer that the same perils and pitfalls await those healthcare practitioners wanting to tackle slip-fall risk. Changing policies and procedures are all good, better staff training and the like is commendable, and anything that reduces falls and injuries is laudable. However, we suggest that architectural design can be brought to bear in the fight against patient falls.

10. WHEN DESIGN HARMS

A brief by Karen Pearson, MLIS, MA, and Andrew Coburn, Ph.D., at the University of Southern Maine, cited CDC research that found most falls occur in inpatient rooms and bathrooms. This data makes sense as patient/procedure rooms are where patients spend most of their time. In addition, those risk factors leading to a high potential for falls – low blood pressure, pain meds, weakened or stiff lower limbs – can affect patient stability, especially when moving from bed to bathroom.

An article by Catherin Gow, AIA, appearing issue of Healthcare Design¹²⁴ magazine points out some of the design failures leading to more significant fall risks:

- Poor access to restrooms. Most patient toilets are seated next to cots, creating pathways for self-transportation from cots to toilets. Often, when patients recover, they think that they cover themselves well enough to get up in theirs without international aid monitors when they cannot walk yet.
- Small restrooms. Historically, population coverage occurs in only one individual and often does not occur at handrails.
- Bad lighting. Most patients' rooms are lit during the daytime, and only one extra light is used at night. Because of this path to the toilet rooms are poor illuminated patients fall.
- Slippery materials. Flooring and other finishing materials cause patients to be more unsteady while using the toilet or shower.

¹²⁴ <https://www.healthcarefacilitiestoday.com/posts/How-the-Pandemic-Influenced-Healthcare-Design--26463>

11. OUTSIDE-THE-BOX DESIGN THINKING

One groundbreaking white paper titled "The Shortest Path to Recovery," authored by Barbara Chastain, RN, and Phil Chisholm at the firm of PageSoutherland Page (PSP) in Houston, Texas, offers some outside-the-box thinking to reduce fall risk in inpatient rooms. This New Approach was implemented at St. Luke's Sugarland Hospital in Sugarland, Texas¹²⁵.

Step 1: Reducing trip distance.

Figure 5. The innovative PSP approach cut transfer distance from patient bed to toilet in half over traditional patient room designs.

According to PSP, the average hospital patient room design requires a 16-foot to 19-foot unassisted trip from bed to the toilet. So the designers crafted a room design that cut the "transfer distance" in half ... just 8 feet to reach the toilet.

125 Planning and designing of specialty healthcare facilities. / SHAKTI KUMAR KANT SUNIL CHANDRASHEKHAR R GUPTA / JAYPEE Brothers MEDICAL P, 2020

Step 2: Patient's room continues handrail.

PSP has added a continuous handrail from the bathroom to the bed to have a sustainable surface. In addition, only 10 percent of the patient rooms must be average for the disabled, and the design features of the random PSP are 100 percent.

Step 3: No turns to the toilet.

In addition to the proximity of the bed to the bathroom, the toilet itself was placed with its back against the closest wall. Once the patient passes the bathroom threshold, it is unnecessary to twist and turn into position because the seat is the same as it approaches the inconspicuous passenger. The door to the bathroom can be met with both an encounter and a discovery directed towards an encounter with the hospital meeting.

12. NEW THINKING NEEDED ON GRAB BARS AND HANDRAILS IN BATHROOMS AND SUMMARY

Grab bars in patient bathrooms are a must, and with good reason: One 2007 study showed that of 7,082 falls collected in nine Midwestern hospitals, 11 percent were in the bathroom.¹²⁶

Researchers Huey-Ming Tseng, Ph.D., RN, and Chang-Yi Yin, MA, at the University of Michigan School Of Nursing have proposed that guidelines for healthcare facility design should be revised to allow a range of grab bar and handrail configurations to meet the needs of various age cadres and those with disabilities.¹²⁷ Specifically, they recommend:

- For acute care hospitals, the authors propose that high–low horizontal grab bars or handrails should be mounted and installed on every part of the patient room walls, every part of the bathroom walls in a patient room, and in the corridors commonly used by patients (e.g., hallways from patient rooms to nurses' stations).

¹²⁶ Adding additional grab bars as a possible strategy for safer hospital stays Tzeng, Huey-Ming et al. Applied Nursing Research, Volume 23 , Issue 1 , 45 - 51

¹²⁷ <https://www.centerfortransforminghealthcare.org/-/media/ctf/documents/what-we-offer/preventing-falls-tst-fact-sheet-8-15.pdf>

- Instead of installing one-height grab bars or handrails, high–low horizontal grab bars or handrails are recommended as such grab bars or handrails may promote even safer ambulation for hospitalized patients (e.g., better fitting for patients with different body heights). High–Low horizontal grab bars or handrails should be mounted with heights of 26 in. (low) and 36 in. (high) above the floor in all areas commonly used by patients. In addition, horizontal bars are suggested because they are easy to grasp and generate push-up force if needed (US Department of Justice, 2002). Short horizontal bars may be more beneficial than vertical bars; some short horizontal bars may be installed appropriately.
- The safety and ease of cleaning are two primary considerations for installing additional grab bars or handrails. The frame of grab bars or handrails should be made of steel tubing with a gripping surface diameter of 1.5 in. and should be able to bear the weight of a patient up to 400 lb. Steel round tubs must have rounded corners to prevent injuries. If grab bars or handrails are mounted adjacent to a wall, the space between the wall and the grab bars or handrails should be at least 1.5 in. to accommodate arthritic patients with swollen fingers.¹²⁸

Like HAIs, hospital patient falls an "epidemic," affecting 1 million patients each year and causing billions of dollars in added – and arguably preventable – treatment expenses and litigation. Worse, 11,000 patients die each year as a result of falls. A well-designed fall prevention protocol and culture can be a positive step in reducing fall incidents. However, as no method is foolproof, designers and hospital staff must think outside the box and incorporate fresh innovations to reduce transfer distances and provide steadying handrails and grab bars that allow patients to move safely in inpatient and procedure room settings.

¹²⁸ Adding additional grab bars as a possible strategy for safer hospital stays Tzeng, Huey-Ming et al. Applied Nursing Research, Volume 23 , Issue 1 , 45 - 51

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OVERALL CONCLUSION

The pandemic has been going on for two years now, and as time goes on, it becomes more and more evident that the virus is not going anywhere. The best way to protect against an endemic such as Covid-19 or other viruses is to follow scientifically provided directives about medications, vaccines, and other preventive measures. An infected person spreads Covid-19 through his mouth or nose in small liquid particles formed through sneezing, coughing, breathing, and speaking it; comes according to the World Health Organization, An uninfected person can directly inhale these particles to contract the virus, or they can land on various surfaces, primarily where people commonly reside and in crowded places, hence contaminating these surfaces. Touching such surfaces and their mouth, eyes, or nose can contract the virus. With AFREN wall protection systems, there can be significant protection against Covid-19 and other viruses contraction because individuals will have protected contact with surfaces. In addition, when applied together with biocides such as ionpure silver, they become extra protected. The wall protection systems are also designed to help curb fall injuries from various structure sections.

COVID-19 AND ITS PREVENTION MECHANISMS

Nowadays, our structures across every corner of our paths are designed or comprised of parts designed to help ensure safety at all times against issues like fires, falls, and contamination. Therefore, safety counts as an essential element of designing, manufacturing, and building construction systems, parts, and structures. Fall accidents can be destructive and crippling to the affected, and although they can be rare, they can also be unforgiving when they take place. When such falls result from indecent, weak, and unsafe structures and structure materials, they can be devastating. Furthermore, the recent past has seen the emergence of Covid-19, which transmits, including through-wall systems at homes and other public and crowded building surfaces.

While working closely with scientists and other medical experts, the Center for Disease Control and Protection (CDC) has been on the frontline in giving health directives to help prevent, treat, and mitigate the spread of Covid-19. One of these measures includes washing

hands thoroughly, mainly because people always touch surfaces on which viruses rest. Other measures include avoiding crowds and poorly ventilated places. These include places like gyms, restaurants, malls, and movie theaters, all of which consist of a fair number of touchable surfaces. Additionally, it reiterates the importance of disinfecting surfaces. This article aims to emphasize how ARFEN wall protection systems can help prevent fall injuries and how in conjunction with biocides, they can be used to mitigate the spread of Covid-19¹²⁹.

SURFACES AS HAZARDS

From being facilitators of contagions, surfaces, particularly indoor-based ones, are an incredible attribute to falls and other forms of injuries. We can hardly live without structures as they facilitate everyday activities, be it taking a shower, riding an escalator or elevator, waiting in a queue, studying, and shopping, among other daily activities. Given that Covid-19 count as the most dangerous contamination disease in recent history, there is no doubt that surfaces have played a crucial role in facilitating the spread of the virus. According to WHO (2020), the Covid-19 virus can survive and remain viable on different surfaces for up to 72 hours, especially if the surface is made of stainless steel. However, the virus can survive for up to four hours on copper surfaces and a day on cardboard surfaces¹³⁰. Surfaces made from these materials vary from doorknobs, desks, doors, elevators, supermarket shelves, and baskets.

Having to touch these surfaces after an infected person has been in contact with them and at the same time coughed or sneezed on them increases the possibility of infection¹³¹. Such is also the case where the infected person may have touched, coughed, or sneezed into their hands and went ahead to touch the mentioned surfaces. There are many credible medical reports that the Covid-19 virus mainly spreads through the air, especially when some people are in close contact and one of them is infected, and that surfaces-led infections are to the minimum. Precisely, the chance of acquiring Covid-19 due to being in contact with a virus-

¹²⁹ <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/prevent-getting-sick/prevention.html>

¹³⁰ <https://apps.who.int/iris/rest/bitstreams/1274400/retrieve#:~:text=Recent%20research%20evaluated%20the%20survival,24%20hours%20on%20cardboard>

¹³¹ Pitol, A. K., & Julian, T. R. (2021). Community transmission of SARS-Cov-2 by surfaces: Risks and risk reduction strategies. *Environmental Science & Technology Letters*, 8(3), 263-269. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.0c00966>

infected surface has been said to be 1 in 10,000¹³². Alternatively, around 33 404 lives in the US are at risk because of the virus-infected surface. Nevertheless, most of these surfaces are located in places that constantly attract crowds of people, making them predisposed to infection.

Surfaces have also been known to cause life-long injuries and even death as people try to navigate along and beside them. Having slippery, handle-less, guard rail-less, handrail-less, and not-properly fitted surfaces can lead to falls for users of such surfaces. According to WHO (2021), falls are the second leading cause of unintentional injury deaths globally. Approximately 680000 people die every year due to falls, and up to 80 percent of them are in the low- and middle-income countries and primarily aged above 60 years¹³³. Lacking promotion for policies and standards for playgrounds where surfaces and heights are rampant contributes to the high number of falls¹³⁴. Therefore, producing and promoting the use of surfaces and products that facilitate proper surfaces could be a significant step in reducing the number of deaths and injuries due to falls.

WALL SYSTEMS APPLICATION IN PREVENTING AGAINST INJURIES AND COVID-19

When considering Covid-19, besides protecting against damage to walls and floors, wall systems should provide a safe environment, and even disinfection processes are not enough. The handrail (including wall surfaces) itself should be proper antibacterial material. Hand Rails are used by people every day in many areas, and they are essential because they offer protection and safety for buildings and people residing within them. They are also helpful for safety protocols on beds, carts, and trolleys because they increase texture in neatly covering handling parts. Handrails are among the wall protection systems that allow height changes in ramps, stairs, and landings without going off the rails. Therefore, wall systems will generally offer quality safety and protection for pedestrians, shoppers, and ordinary people going up and

¹³² Pathak, N. (2021, August 9). *Surface cleaning and COVID-19: What you should know*. WebMD. <https://www.webmd.com/lung/how-long-covid-19-lives-on-surfaces>

¹³³ WHO. (2021, April 26). *Falls*. WHO | World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/falls>

¹³⁴ Constro Facilitator. (2021, August 7). *Different types of fall protection systems*. <https://www.constrofacilitator.com/different-types-of-fall-protection-systems/>

down buildings and traffic. They are critical in protecting against slippery areas and flat surfaces, particularly for people with vision impairment or needing extra guidance to navigate some places. Wall protection systems protect the durability of walls and floors and reduce the likelihood of accidents, injury, and litigious action against building owners due to mishaps here and there regarding navigating the buildings.¹³⁵

Therefore, as we see, handrails, corner guards, wall guards, and wall surfaces are initially designed to ensure building and structure safety, but as it turns out today, it is not enough - they need to be safe and help to reduce the spread of virus and bacteria. ARFEN has advanced its production methods and unique materials and provided a wide range of products meant to reach this goal. Recognizing that most of the places and built areas where wall protection systems are installed are also constantly frequented by people, it is fundamental to consider that the systems should also protect the people from contagions like Covid-19 or other viruses, and cleaning their surfaces and the surfaces on which they rest is just different method but not the primary if the material itself can not guarantee the protection from such contagions. For instance, handrail surfaces should be cleanable to reduce the amounts of bacteria and viruses on them without any sort of reaction to the disinfecting agents, and if they are antibacterial, then there is no need for additional cleaning products to be used, and at the same time, it is doubtful that the cleaning process follows the requirements. Arfen wall base material facilitates the hygiene requirements of surfaces in places like schools, laboratories, hospitals, and malls and offers flexibility or high resistance to thermal and humidity fluctuations. They have been helpful in that length, particularly in high hygiene places like labs, dining halls, and hospitals, significantly reducing the virus population on their surfaces.

ECONOMIC COMPONENT

In the following table, we will see the comparative prices of ARFEN products with other "analogs." The word analogs are taken in brackets because ARFEN products are similar to analogs only in their shape, and indeed, in terms of preventing injuries from falls, they all play approximately the same role. However, to reduce the spread of viruses, ARFEN products stand

¹³⁵ Latham Australia. (2022). *Wall protection systems*. Latham Australia - Premium Architectural Products. <https://www.latham-australia.com/wall-protection-systems>

out due to silver ions in the material and active biocides that naturally prevent the spread of pathogens. During the coronavirus pandemic, we all became eyewitnesses of how the speed of the spread of diseases affects the economy and people's lives. Moreover, therefore, it is necessary to consider the importance of constant exposure to unique surfaces to reduce the spread of diseases. Once again, we note that based on the above tests, the surface of ARFEN products reduces the spread of viruses by 99.9%. Impure silver in ARFEN products is fundamental material in our day-to-day activities since its antimicrobial metal ions and insoluble nature facilitates its ability to remain safe. Although it typically comes in glass, the chemical inertness of the resulting glass is lowered such that the structure is continuously altered, particularly in water. The technology has enabled glass chemical inertness by releasing metal ions of silver and copper when in contact with water that gradually acts as antimicrobial material. For this reason, the ionpure has been used in making many applications materials such as gauze masks, disposable gloves, hospital floors, stationery, curtain, white dress, measuring instruments, wallpaper, and flooring materials¹³⁶. Since Covid-19 has proven to significantly require the application of water-based substances for cleaning and disinfecting, these materials can provide a significantly safe environment by reducing the spread of viruses.

Picture of ARFEN product	Name	Prices are given in meters and feet. For ease of analysis, prices are given in meters and feet.			
		ARFEN	"Analog" 1	"Analog" 2	"Analog" 3
	Handrail wall guard	46.17\$/m or 14.07\$/ft # https://arfenusa.com/products/product4	57.35\$/m or 17.49\$/ft # https://wallguard.com/handrails/hospital-handrail/2000-handrail-6-1-4-high.html	116.63\$/m or 35.56\$/ft # https://www.inprocorp.com/products/door-and-wall-protection/handrails/1200-series/	86.02\$/m or 26.23\$/ft # https://www.graingr.com/product/PAWLING-CORP-Handrail-Interior-33UA95

¹³⁶ Ishizuka. (2022). *Inorganic silver antimicrobial "IONPURE"*. 「モノづくり」 「ヒトづくり」 「ユメづくり」 総合容器メーカー 石塚硝子株式会社. <https://www.ishizuka.co.jp/english/material/antimicrobial/#date01>

Picture of ARFEN product	Name	Prices are given in meters and feet. For ease of analysis, prices are given in meters and feet.			
		ARFEN	"Analog" 1	"Analog" 2	"Analog" 3
	Handrail System	17.33\$/m or 5.28\$/ft # https://arfenusa.com/products/product10	18.42\$/m or 5.6\$/ft # https://wallguard.com/handrails/cylindrical-profile-handrails/2035-handrail-1-1-2-diameter.html	40.63\$/m or 12.38\$/ft # https://www.inprocorp.com/products/door-and-wall-protection/handrails/900-series/	28.59\$/m or 8.71\$/ft # https://www.grainger.com/product/PAWLING-CORP-Handrail-Interior-33UC07
	Wall Guard	25.03\$/m or 7.63\$/ft # https://arfenusa.com/products/product14	36.56\$/m or 11.14\$/ft # https://wallguard.com/wallguards-crash-rails/flat-profile-wallguards/2125-wallguard-series.html	69.74\$/m or 21.26\$/ft # https://www.inprocorp.com/products/door-and-wall-protection/wall-guards/1600-series/	Unknown
	Corner Guard	21.04\$/m or 6.41\$/ft # https://arfenusa.com/products/product10	29.15\$/m or 8.88\$/ft # https://wallguard.com/corner-guards/high-impact-corner-guards/vinyl-corner-guards.html	50.60\$/m or 15.42\$/ft # https://www.inprocorp.com/products/door-and-wall-protection/corner-guards/150/	61.95\$/m or 18.88\$/ft # https://www.grainger.com/product/GRAINGER-APPROVED-Corner-Guard-3-in-Wd-5MKF9

Picture of ARFEN product	Name	Prices are given in meters and feet. For ease of analysis, prices are given in meters and feet.			
		ARFEN	"Analog" 1	"Analog" 2	"Analog" 3
	Rigid Vinyl Sheet* (price is given in sqm and sqft)	21.04\$/sqm or 1.95\$/sqft # https://arfenusa.com/products/product10	55.49\$/m or 5.15\$/ft # https://wallguard.com/vinyl-sheet/2400.1-.060-vinyl-sheet.html	59.78\$/sqm or 5.55\$/sqft # https://www.inprocorp.com/products/door-and-wall-protection/palladium-rigid-sheet-wall-protection/rigid-sheet/	Unknown

This table shows only a part of the position, which accurately reflects the groups of each position.

In the Handrail wall guard position, as we can see, ARFEN makes it possible for an American buyer to buy up to 252% more or save 20-60% compared to "analogs." In addition to this, with ARFEN products, the consumer receives a product from a particular composition with an active antiviral effect, which will work all the time for the benefit of the consumer and society by reducing the number of viral diseases transmitted through the surface.

Wall Protection Handrail wall guards help protect humans from fall injuries, walls at their length, for instance, through a corridor from getting damaged and reduce the massive spread of viral diseases due to the active biocide (ionpure silver) in the material. Wall guards are customarily applied on columns, walls, and door entrances to prevent crashes and impacts. They are mainly used in Health Care, Hospitality, and Schools. The images above represent ARFEN's WG145 Handrail wall guard, WG152 Handrail wall guard, and DC140 Handrail wall guard.

In the Handrail system position, as we can see, ARFEN makes it possible for an American buyer to buy up to 234% more or save 6-57% compared to "analogs." In addition to this, with ARFEN products, the consumer receives a product from a particular composition with an active antiviral effect, which will work all the time for the benefit of the consumer and society by reducing the number of viral diseases transmitted through the surface.

Wall Protection Handrail system helps protect humans from fall injuries, walls at their length, for instance, through a corridor from getting damaged and reduces the massive spread of viral diseases due to the active biocide (ionpure silver) in the material. Wall guards are typically applied on columns, walls, and door entrances to prevent crashes and impacts. They are mainly used in Health Care, Hospitality, and Schools. The images above represent ARFEN's WG42-1 Handrail system, WG50 Handrail system, and WG42 Handrail system.

In the Wall guard position, as we can see, ARFEN makes it possible for an American buyer to buy up to 278% more or save 32-65% compared to "analogs." In addition to this, with ARFEN products, the consumer receives a product from a unique composition with an active antiviral effect, which will work all the time for the benefit of the consumer and society by reducing the number of viral diseases transmitted through the surface.

Like Wall Protection Wall guards, they also help protect walls at their length, for instance, through a corridor from getting damaged, and reduce the massive spread of viral diseases due to the active biocide (ionpure silver) in the material. Wall guards usually are applied on columns, walls, and door entrances to prevent crashes and impacts. They are mainly used in Health Care, Hospitality, and Schools. ARFEN's version of wall guards is shown above WG150 Wall guard, DC200 Wall guard, and WG200 Wall guard.

In the Corner Guard position, as we can see, ARFEN makes it possible for an American buyer to buy up to 294% more or save 28-66% compared to "analogs." In addition to this, with ARFEN products, the consumer receives a product from a particular composition with an active antiviral effect, which will work all the time for the benefit of the consumer and society by reducing the number of viral diseases transmitted through the surface.

Wall protection corner guards protect surfaces such as doors, floors, and walls from damage, primarily when heavy loads are carried close to these surfaces, and reduce the massive spread of viral diseases due to the active biocide (ionpure silver) in the material. They help soften the impacts that could have been due to damage and increase the level of protection from impacts. They are mainly used in Health Care, Hospitality, and Schools. The above images show ARFEN's CG50B Tape-on corner guard, CG50 Corner guard system, and CG76A Corner guard system 135°.

In the Rigid vinyl sheet position, as we can see, ARFEN makes it possible for an American buyer to buy up to 284% more or save 62-65% compared to "analogs." In addition to this, with ARFEN products, the consumer receives a product from a particular composition with an active antiviral effect, which will work all the time for the benefit of the consumer and society by reducing the number of viral diseases transmitted through the surface.

Wall Protection Rigid sheet wall protection helps protect walls from scratches, scrapes, and dents and reduces the massive spread of viral diseases due to the material's active biocide (ionpure silver). They are mainly used in Health Care, Hospitality, Schools, and Laboratories. The figure shows ARFEN's 1004 Rigid Vinyl Sheet application in hospital corridors, intensive care rooms, and operating rooms.

SUMMARY

We all know that according to the White House Strategy Names 20 Emerging Technologies Crucial to National Security¹³⁷ their strategy includes an initial list of 20 technologies identified as critical by the National Security Council, and one of them is Medical and public health technologies. The strategy for developing the Healthcare system is based on simple the basic principles of maintaining the health and quality of life of the population, using modern technologies, and being open to the new, which can contribute to the goal of the strategy. In connection with this, we can safely say that ARFEN products can be effectively used in many areas as a finishing material (different handrails and wall materials), effectively fighting the spread of viruses, reducing their spread to 99.99%. In modern society, each has an active social life; we work and study, meet in public places with our loved ones and friends, and want to know and feel safe. Moreover, we can even now feel it in our children. How often before this pandemic did we see our children dry their hands or clean them every five minutes? This was not often the case, and they had more freedom than now. Moreover, one of the reasons that our children and we also have to use sanitizers all the time is that most surfaces do not protect us in any way and, as the practice has shown, it would be it is better than the majority of surfaces protect us. The health system of the population is like a giant puzzle consisting of small parts, and each part plays a significant role in this team game at certain times. Taking into account the fact that ARFEN products with an active antiviral effect with ionpure silver, which can be used in many areas, and the underlying production technology meets the requirements of the strategic task of preserving the lives and quality of life of the population, it could play a significant role in this fight against various viral phenomena.

¹³⁷ <https://www.nextgov.com/emerging-tech/2020/10/white-house-strategy-names-20-emerging-technologies-crucial-national-security/169293/>